

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

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Uses and Gratifications of the Internet and Search Engines for Academic Purposes Among Heritage Polytechnic Students

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Abstract

This research examines the uses and gratifications of the Internet and search engines for academic purposes among Heritage Polytechnic (Heripoly) students, Eket, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. It aims at finding out students' frequency of utilising these tools for academic purposes; to ascertain the academic activities for which students utilise the Internet and search engines; and to determine if students' utilisation of the Internet and search engines has any positive influence on their academic performance. To achieve this, questionnaires were used as instruments for data collection. A survey was conducted on 360 students of the institution, and it was revealed that students use the Internet and search engines occasionally for sundry academic purposes such as term papers, seminars, projects, researches; assignments, and preparation for examinations and tests. Other uses of the Internet include general topic reading, audio-visual tutorials, spellings; grammar and pronunciation checks, and so on. Students reported real gratifications from Wikipedia and Google most. The study recommends that education policy makers and management of institutions of higher level evolve with digital technology to enhance innovative research via custom-made mobile electronic library gadgets, powered by unlimited network access to facilitate students' quest for computer-based academic resources.

Keywords: Internet, Digitisation, Internetalisation, Search Engines, Emerging Media, Gratifications, Academic Purposes

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Introduction

There is hardly any aspect of human endeavour that digitisation has not impacted. Within the traditional African educational setting, for instance, the Internet and search engines have dramatically redefined how students approach research and access learning materials and educational resources. As Callaghan (2019) notes, the Internet and search engines have armed learners with tools to build knowledge and develop their academic opportunities beyond the physical classroom setting. Emerging technological inventions in the realms of information and communication technologies (ICTs) have greatly impacted on the quality and process of educational data storage, retrieval and distribution. This development has had tremendous influence on the process of making academic resources and learning materials available to distant learners in order to pursue and explore educational opportunities and advancements. Hence, utility of emerging media tools such as the Internet and search engines in this regard seems to be quite promising with fulfilling potentials to enhance and facilitate educational development.

In the 21st Century, the inputs, resources and data necessary for knowledge transfer, acquisition and building are solely at the mercy of technological inventions and innovations such as the Internet and search engines. There is no gainsaying the fact that these innovations are permeating (on a constant and torrential basis) the educational nerve centres of virtually every nation of the world that is driven by knowledge economy. The robust impact of the Internet and search engines on the knowledge economy of any nation is so overwhelming that educational development become impracticable and unattainable without them. The Internet and search engines are inseparable part of today's educational system to the extent that the academic community - teachers, instructors, lecturers and the learners - increasingly depend on them for sundry purposes (Lekganyane, Lesele, Makwela, Mathole, Nemutanzhela & Mbedzi, 2014).

The extent to which the Internet and search engines are used for academic and educational purposes are so profound that over-reliance and overtly dependency on the ICTs tools seems to threaten the existence, relevance, utility as well as the place of hard copy or material books and instructors in a learning process and attendant educational development. Prior to the advent, adoption and proliferation of the Internet and search engines, material books enjoyed uncontested monopoly as the sole and principal

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reservoir of knowledge. Learners and instructors alike would seek titles and volumes of interest. Books were sacred to learners and instructors; invaluable and indispensable tools for educational development and advancement. However, with the rise of the Internet and search engines, even the nature, distribution and consumption of books have so changed that learners deploy the Internet and search engines to access current volumes of educational contents than a typical hard copy.

It should be noted, however, that despite the wanton benefits and potentials that the Internet and search engines bring in the learning process, the value, relevance and role of books cannot be supplanted but rather enhanced by the potentials of the Internet and search engines. That new media technologies such as the Internet and search engines transform and enhance educational advancement validates Roger Fiddler's "mediamorphosis" hypothetical prognosis that technological evolution of communication media do not just occur spontaneously or self-existing, but take roots and footing from (pre-)existing media (Fiddler, 1997). This is to say that the Internet and search engines emerging as new forms of media for academic/educational resources draw their educational resourcefulness from the nature and characteristic of books.

The Internet and search engines have not only changed the teacher-learner landscape and tutelage narratives but have also influenced learner-classroom relationship. The classroom has changed from the four walls of a building accommodating more than one learner and an instructor interrogating the learning space to a 'gadgetised' environment where a learner, with the aid of, or in accompaniment of a device that supports Internet and search engines services, can access a personalised learning experience at his/her convenience.

Today, the prospects that came with the invention of the printing press and the promising nature of printed materials as principal sources for knowledge acquisition have been completely overwhelmed and impacted upon by the Internet and search engines. The Internet and search engines, in their nature, can be characterised as being super-active, super-fast, multi-faceted and super-intelligent learning technologies that avail a learner's academic information search efforts in 'nano' seconds with learning resources whose quality and quantity are undoubtedly substantial. At the speed of light, these emerging learning technologies can multiply search efforts, processes and activities and produce the needed result accurately in less time. These technologies are changing the information and communication landscape and their impact on knowledge

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building, acquisition; transfer and sharing are no less profound. Printed materials, once relied upon for knowledge building, acquisition, transfer and sharing are now treading the brink of extinction. Thus, the advent of the Internet and search engines has significantly ushered in the emergence of a new form of knowledge production and distribution: the soft form (Ivwithreghweta & Igere, 2014). Ayub, Hamid & Nawawi (2014, p. 233) capture the point succinctly:

Advances in computer technology have enabled the Internet to serve as a platform not merely to seek information, but also to exchange ideas and knowledge with other users, and obtain expert opinions via email, teleconferencing, chatting and other avenues. Nevertheless, the advent of social network sites such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and others that include chatting and online games have changed the perception on Internet use from one that is associated with learning to that of a socializing facility. Such website applications have resulted in the Internet being used for both academic and non-academic activities.

From the foregoing, there is hardly any “info-educational” process, activities or idea that is not influenced by technological innovativeness of the Internet and search engines. This study comes on the heels of ascertaining the uses and gratifications of the Internet and search engines for academic purposes by Heritage Polytechnic students.

Statement of the Problem

The Internet and search engines are resourceful information and communication technologies (ICTs) as far as information sourcing, distant learning and knowledge building are concerned. When properly utilised, the innovations could yield qualitative and quantitative knowledge base, and resources for students to consult and obtain relevant knowledge-based contents. The reasons for the above statement stems from the fact that there is hardly any topic, issue or content that cannot be found on the Internet when sourced for by the search engines. The perceived inexhaustibility of the Internet and search engines has made their usefulness quite irreplaceable. This, thus raises concerns as to what uses students put them into in relation to their (students’) academic activities.

Though it may be assumed that the students have, at some points, given their academic purposes, utilised the Internet and search engines, it is not certain whether such utilisation has yielded any meaningful benefits. It is not also established whether

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students' Internet and search engines usage have any correlation with their academic performances. To this end, huge research gap exists in the study of Internet and search engine use for academic activities. In view of this, the study raises the question: Are Heritage Polytechnic students satisfied with their use of the Internet and search engines for academic purposes?

Objectives of the Study

The study sets out to:

- i. find out heritage polytechnic students' frequency of utilising the Internet and search engines for academic purposes;
- ii. find out the academic activities or purposes they utilise the Internet and search engines for;
- iii. find out the internet sites and search engines frequently utilised by Heritage Polytechnic students for academic purposes;
- iv. ascertain if heritage polytechnic students' academic needs for utilising the internet and search engines are satisfied;
- v. ascertain the challenges besetting heritage polytechnic students' utilisation of the internet and search engines for academic purposes;
- vi. determine if heritage polytechnic students' utilisation of the internet and search engines have any positive influence on their academic performance

The "Internetisation" of Academic Resources

Internet refers to the interconnectivity between two or more computers networked or linked together by a remote server in order to retrieve, share or transfer data. If relevance is when such data have educational value, which is the potential to teach, transfer or impart knowledge beyond the classroom setting, it is tempting to submit that one of the greatest blessings at man's disposal in the 21st century is the invention and proliferation of the Internet to drive educationally-beneficial concerns and objectives. The Internet is very sensitive to the survival of human race and the functioning of the information society that there is hardly any human endeavour that has not been impacted by this innovative invention. Learning and instructing in the modern age seems to be a lot easier when "internetised".

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“Internetisation” is a concept that embodies the robust and wholesome influence of the Internet on the production, archival, retrieval, sharing, consulting, accessibility, utilisation and distribution of academic resources with recourse to how, where and when they can be accessed and for what purpose. It paints a lucid picture of academic resources being overwhelmed and permeated by the impact and utility of the internet to the extent that the former would not be possibly made available without the latter. This is a situation where the nitty-gritty of academic resources are being subjected or maneuvered by the innovativeness of the Internet.

The gains and benefits that come with the usage of the Internet are divinely profound, technologically awe-inspiring, economically viable and educationally robust. People from all walks of life use the Internet for their personal needs (which include learning new things). As an increasing number of citizens use the Internet for communication, entertainment, information, education, simple “connectedness” as a result of Internet access and time spent online are no longer sufficient indices to gauge whether a “divide” still characterises the digital world” (Lekganyane, et al., 2014). Hence, the utilisation of the Internet for learning and other academic purposes is seen as a means to improve accessibility, efficiency and quality of learning by facilitating access to resources and services as well as remote exchanges and collaboration (Kamba 2009 in Ivwighreghweta & Igere, 2014).

Search Engines and Learning

Search engines are information retrieval systems that can collect extensive information using queries or keywords (Kurniasih, Kurniawati, Yulianti, Rahim, Sujito, Ikhwan, Aimang, Haluti, Putri, & Napitupul, 2018). It can be likened to a vault where valuable collections are kept for a pre-determined purpose. It can also be seen as information and knowledge store house whose potentiality can only be realised when linked to Internet-enabled or web-based technological innovations.

The role of Search engines is significant in growing the habit of reading and learning in the digital era (Kurniasih, 2016). This is validated in the claim that vast resources for educational purposes are chipped in the Internet. By taking learners to collaborative or interconnected web-resources locations that archived the academic material sourced for and making it accessible for the learner, the Search engines facilitate the learning process.

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The Internet and Search Engines: The symbiosis

Search engines, without the Internet, are nothing but a well-decorated automobile with square wheels and tires: very useless for transportation but a concrete expression of cosmetic misapplication. This is to say that the search engines are driven by Internet and network innovations. The Internet bequeaths the Search Engines with technicalities, innovations and drivers to be useful. The Search Engines, on the other hand points Internet-surfers to the right destination to get the educational resources/data they are searching for by collaborating with interconnected websites, blogs or web-pages (that house contents searched for) to make such experience worthwhile. Here lies the symbiotic relationship between the Internet and the search engines.

The Internet and search engines make possible the virtual classroom. A virtual classroom is an online teaching environment. According to Callaghan (2019), “the environment can be web-based and requires downloadable executable file. Just like in a real world classroom, a student in a virtual classroom participates in synchronous instruction, which means that the teacher and students are logged into the virtual teaching environment at the same time. Just as the term virtual means a simulation of the real thing, a virtual classroom is a simulated classroom via the Internet, which provides a convenient communication environment for distance learners just like face-to-face classroom”. In sum, with the Internet and the search engines, teachers and students enjoy a teaching-learning experience that is similar to a real classroom.

Theoretical Framework

The Uses and Gratifications Theory

The primary groundwork to the Uses and Gratifications theory was laid by Jay Blumler and Denis McQuail in 1969. Uses and Gratification Theory is an audience-centered approach that focuses on what people do with the media and not what the media do to people. The theory is concerned primarily with the use to which people put the media such as the Internet and search engines into, and the attendant pre-conceived needs to be satisfied in such exercise. It has less concern on the effect the media being used wield on the media user or audience.

A functional analysis of the theory as advanced by Klapper (1963), cited in Ruggiero (2000), positions the audience member as active consumer of dynamic streams of mass communicated messages, rather than classifying them as passive

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(almost inert) role in media content consumption to which many earliest theories relegated them. The theory reflects a shift from the traditional effects models and theories of mass media consumption to a more functionalist theoretical perspective (Ruggiero, 2000).

Uses and Gratification Theory provides a vista of how and why Heritage Polytechnic students interact with the Internet and search engines and for what academic purposes or needs. Its relevance to this study is underscored by the fact that it is a media-use theory, deeply concentrated on gratifications sought and gratifications or outcomes obtained after utilising the media for a personalised need (Rayburn, 1996). As new technologies, the Internet and search engines empower the academic world with novel, alternative education and learning resources; therefore, analysis of the utility of these ICTs tools in servicing educational concerns and the satisfaction learners get from using such tools becomes very necessary.

The questions that a review of the Uses and Gratification theory seem to preempt are: why do Heritage Polytechnic students use the Internet and search engines for academic activities; what usefulness does such usage have on their academic performance; and, are the students satisfied with their choices of using the Internet and search as their academic resources? Providing answers to these set of questions indicates the relevance of the theory to the study. The gratifications sought and gained would influence continuous use, while gratification sought and not gained could motivate them to discontinue the use of the Internet and search engines for academic purposes. Hence, the theory determines the motives that lead to Internet and search engines usage by Heritage Polytechnic students and the personal and psychological rewards that result from such usage (Wimmer & Dominick, 2011).

Methodology

This research paper adopted the survey research design, with the questionnaire as instrument for data collection. The population of the study comprised 3,621 Heritage Polytechnic full-time/regular students of the 2019/2020 academic session. Using the Taro Yamene's formula, a sample size of 360 was drawn from the population. And to reach to the respondents, a multi-stage sampling procedure was adopted to select respondents from departments in the faculties of Engineering and Management Sciences of the Institution.

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Findings, Analysis and Discussion

Of the 360 copies of the questionnaires administered, 352 (98%) copies were retrieved and found suitable for the analysis of data for this study. Analyses are as follows:

Table I: Heritage Polytechnic students' frequency of using the Internet and Search Engines for any academic purpose(s)

Frequency	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Daily	61	17
Weekly	28	8
Bi-weekly	13	4
Monthly	19	5
Bi-monthly	11	3
Quarterly	-	-
Per-semester	37	11
Yearly	-	-
Occasionally	99	28
Often	84	24
Never	-	-
Total	352	100

The data analysed in Table I show that majority of Heritage Polytechnic students (99 [28%]) used the Internet and Search Engines for academic purposes occasionally. Occasional use of the Internet and search engines by the students implies that their usage was pre-determined and orchestrated by an academic task-assignment or project that warrants or necessitated such usage. Hence, usage was causal and premeditated. It therefore means that students of the polytechnic that had more academic tasks or assignment to undertake would most likely engage the Internet and search engines on a frequent basis compared to those with lesser academic task to undertake.

A detailed analysis of data analysed in the table reveal this situation more lucidly. It shows that 61 [17%] students utilised the Internet and search engines for

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academic purposes on a daily basis; 28 [8%] students utilised the Internet and search engines for academic purposes on a weekly basis; 13 [4%] students utilised the Internet and search engines for academic purposes bi-weekly (twice a week); 19 [5%] students utilised the Internet and search engines for academic purposes on a monthly basis; 11 [3%] students utilised the Internet and search engines for academic purposes bi-monthly (twice a week); 37 [11%] students utilised the Internet and search engines for academic purposes per-semester; 84 [24%] students utilised the Internet and search engines for academic purposes often while none of the students utilised the Internet and search engines for academic purposes quarterly (every three months) and yearly basis. All these point to the fact that all the sampled students of the polytechnic have at one point in time put the resourcefulness of the Internet and search engines to use in view of expected academic needs gratification.

Table II: Other Sources of Academic Information to Heritage Polytechnic Students aside the Internet and Search Engines

Sources of Information	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
The library	113	32
Books	192	54
Focused Group Discussion	-	-
Interview	-	-
Radio	9	3
Television	27	8
Social media	11	3
Total	352	100

The analysis of data in Table II reveals that majority of 192 (54%) Heritage Polytechnic students' alternative source of academic information was books. Hence, in the absence of the Internet and search engines, books were widely consulted by the students in view of meeting their academic needs and expectations. Further findings from the analysis in the table reveal that offline library was alternatively use by 113 [32%] students of the polytechnic; radio served as alternative academic resource to 9 [3%] students of the

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polytechnic; 27 [8%] of the students resorted to television as academic resource in the absence of the Internet and search engines while social media platforms were academic resource avenue to 11 [3%] students of the polytechnic. This confirms that alternative media use for academic purposes by Heritage Polytechnic students depends on their perceived satisfactions, needs, wishes or motives (McQuail, 2005).

Table III: Academic activities or purposes for which Heritage Polytechnic Students use the Internet and Search Engines

Academic Purposes/Activities	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Seminar materials	14	3
Project/research materials	41	12
Assignment materials	22	6
Term paper materials	76	22
Examination reading materials	11	3
Test preparatory materials	10	3
General topic reading	23	7
Audio-visual tutorials	18	5
Spellings, grammar and pronunciation checks	23	7
Graphical/pictorial illustrations	16	4
Knowledge confirmation	38	11
Information cross-referencing	42	12
Bibliographical purposes	18	5
Total	352	100

The data analysed in Table III show that 76 (22%) students of Heritage Polytechnic used the Internet and search engines to source for academic materials for their term papers. Further findings of the study reveal that the polytechnic students used the Internet and search engines to source for, locate or consult study materials to aid their academic performances. Some of the areas they used the Internet and search engines to source for materials were: seminar (14 [3%]); project/research (41 [12%]); assignments (22[6%]);

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examination reading purposes (11 [3%]); test preparation (10 [3%]); general topic reading (23 [7%]); audio-visual tutorials (18 [5%]); spellings, grammar and pronunciation checks (23 [7%]); graphical/pictorial illustrations (16 [4%]); knowledge confirmation (38 [11%]); information cross-referencing (42 [12%]) and bibliographical purposes (18 [5%]).

Table IV: Internet Sites Frequently Visited by Students of Heritage Polytechnic for Academic Purpose(s).

Internet sites	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
www.wikipedia.org	124	35
www.google.com.ng	109	31
www.pdfdrive.com	23	7
www.bookboon.com	19	5
www.investopedia.com	18	5
www.bigthink.com	11	3
https://www.inspire.com	9	3
www.coursera.org	7	2
www.nouncourseware.org	7	2
www.brightstorm.com	6	2
www.cosmolearning.com	6	2
www.howcast.com	5	1
www.academicearth.org	5	1
www.udacity.com	3	1
Total	352	100

Analysis on the table shows that majority of the students (124 [35%]) visited www.wikipedia.org, closely-followed by www.google.com.ng (109 [31%]). This presupposes that www.wikipedia.org and www.google.com.ng are very popular among the students in terms of their academic resourcefulness, wealth of contents, accessibility and availability of quality academic materials.

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Other Internet sites that Heritage Polytechnic students utilised for their academic purposes were: www.pdfdrive.com (23[7%]); www.bookboon.com (19[5%]); www.investopedia.com (18 [5%]); www.bigthink.com (11 [3%]); <https://www.inspire.com> (9 [3%]); www.coursera.org (7[2%]); www.nouncourseware.org (7[2%]); www.brightstorm.com (6 [2%]); www.cosmolearning.com (6[2%]); www.howcast.com (5[1%]); (5 [1%]) and www.udacity.com (3[1%]).

Table V: Search Engines frequently used by Heritage Polytechnic Students for Academic Purposes

Search Engines	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Google	148	42
Ask.com	67	19
AoL	26	7
Bing	18	5
Yahoo	81	23
Baidu	9	3
Excite	3	1
DuckDuckGo	-	-
Wolfram Alpha	-	-
Yandex	-	-
Lycos	-	-
Chacha.com	-	-
Total	352	100

The analysis of data on Table V above indicates that 148 (42%) students of Heritage Polytechnic frequently use the *Google* search engine for their academic purposes. This indicates that *Google* search engine is popular among the students of the Polytechnic and it is famous for its rich educational or academic contents.

Other findings in this regard reveal that 67 [19%] students of Heritage Polytechnic utilised *Ask.com*; 26 [7%] the students utilised *AoL*; 18 [5%] the students

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utilised *Bing*; 81 [23%] students of the polytechnic utilised *Yahoo*; 9 [3%] the students utilised *Baidu*; 3 [1%] students utilised *Excite* Search Engines for their academic purposes while none of the students utilised *DuckDuckGo*; *Wolfram Alpha*; *Yandex*; *Lycos* and *Chacha.com* search engines in this regard. The justification may be that the search engines were not popular or did not have rich search factors as well as being unfulfilling to the students' academic search efforts.

Table VI: Challenges encountered by the Students of Heritage Polytechnic as they use Internet and Search Engines for academic purposes

Challenges	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
High cost of data bundle	48	14
Inadequate electricity power supply	31	9
Network failure/fluctuations	108	31
Irrelevant web contents	9	3
Aggressive interstitials/Pop Up ads	13	4
Hack/security issues	92	26
Virus attacks	43	12
Lack of device	8	2
Poor browsing skills	-	-
Total	352	100

The analysis on Table VI reveals that majority of 108 (31%) students of Heritage Polytechnic faced network failure and fluctuations in the course of using the Internet and search engines for academic purposes. Further findings reveal that high cost of data bundle (48 [14%]); inadequate electricity power supply (31 [9%]); irrelevant web contents (9 [3%]); aggressive interstitials/pop up ads (13 [4%]); hacking/security issues (92 [26%]); virus attacks (43 [12%]) and lack of device (8 [2%]) were other daunting challenges that Heritage Polytechnic students encountered in the course of utilising the Internet and search engines for their academic activities. Findings also reveal that none of the students of the polytechnic had challenge bothering on their technical knowledge of the operations of the Internet and search engines.

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Table VII: Responses on whether Heritage Polytechnic Students' needs for the utilisation of the Internet and Search Engines for academic purposes have been satisfactory

Responses	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	221	63
Agree	47	13
Neutral/undecided	20	6
Disagree	43	12
Strongly disagree	21	6
Total	352	100

The analysis of data on Table VII reveals that majority of 221 (63%) Heritage Polytechnic students' needs for the utilisation of the Internet and search engines for academic purposes have been satisfied. Other findings indicate that 6% of the students were indecisive as to whether they were satisfied with Internet and search engines usage for academic purposes while 18% of the students were not satisfied with the potentiality and usefulness of the Internet and search engines to address their academic concerns. The findings of the study imply that Internet and search engines usage (though their utility satisfies up to 76% of the students' academic needs), did not entirely satisfy 24% of the students. Hence, satisfaction or gratification sought and gained from usage of the Internet and search engines among the students was not total, universal or uniformly fashioned but it varied based on certain technical, psychographic and demographic factors.

Table VIII: Responses on whether the Internet and Search Engines have helped in improving Heritage Polytechnic students' academic fortunes

Responses	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	189	54
Agree	71	20
Neutral/undecided	18	5
Disagree	33	9
Strongly disagree	41	12
Total	352	100

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The data analysis in Table VIII shows that majority of 189 (54%) students of Heritage Polytechnic use of the Internet and search engines have positively influenced their academic performance. Hence, by using the Internet and search engines as academic resource tools, they gained access to array of educational resources and knowledge-building materials to undertake academic activities such as term papers (22%); seminar (3%); project/research (12%); assignments (6%); examination reading purposes (3%); test preparation (3%); general topic reading (7%); audio-visual tutorials (5%); spellings, grammar and pronunciation checks (7%); graphical/pictorial illustrations (4%); knowledge confirmation (11%); information cross-referencing (12%); and bibliographical purposes (5%). Such exposure to academic resources and materials boosts the academic performances of the students.

The implication of this finding is that since the Internet and search engines afford the students access to relevant academic resource materials, they could undertake their academic tasks and assignments smoothly. To this end, they could turn in assignment, term papers, and seminars on time; and also have materials to read up for examination and continuous assessment test. All these help to improve their academic performances. This is a way of saying that the utilisation of the Internet and search engines avails the students of Heritage Polytechnic the substantial pools, amount and volumes of educational resources and materials on varied relevant subject matters, topics, issues and disciplines that upon being consulted or read, widen or deepen the intellectual depths of the students. As the students' intellectual depths presumably get widened or deepened, their intelligent quotient increases. This development most likely place the students at a vantage knowledge position to attend to academic exercises such as tests, assignments, term papers, research and examination with productive efforts.

Table IX: Responses on whether Heritage Polytechnic Students rely heavily on the Internet and Search Engines for academic purposes

Responses	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	237	67
Agree	92	26
Neutral/undecided	7	2
Disagree	5	1
Strongly Disagree	11	3
Total	352	100

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

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The analysis of data in Table IX shows that majority of 237 (67%) Heritage Polytechnic students relied heavily on the Internet and search engines for academic purposes. This may presumably be as a result of the availability and unwarranted access to the vast pool, collection and volume of educational resources such as books, journal articles, reference materials, etc. presented by the Internet and search engines. Being resourceful tools in this regard, the Internet and search engines can hardly be outdone with as the students constantly made use of them in solving their academically-related problems, challenges and issues. Usefulness and the gratification gained from utilising the Internet and search engines are the two triggers that motivate and propel Heritage Polytechnic students' over-reliance on them.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study has established that students of Heritage Polytechnic use the Internet and search engines for sundry academic endeavours. However, any of such utility has not come without challenges such as broadband and service provider failures, inadequate power supply, web security, and inability to afford data bundles, and so on. In the light of these findings, the following recommendations are made:

- I. Management of Heritage Polytechnic should consult ICTs companies to innovate a custom-made mobile electronic library gadgets powered by unlimited network access to facilitate the students' quest for academic materials on the Internet and search engines.
- ii. Telecommunication service providers should improve the quality of their network signals so as not to truncate the students' efforts in searching for academic resource materials on the Internet and search engines.
- iii. Telecommunication service providers should cut down on their data tariff or they invent students' data package where students can access academic-related sites and search engines almost for free in order to encourage them.
- iv. Parents and guardians of Heritage Polytechnic students should avail their wards with wherewithal to access academic resource materials on the Internet and search engines.
- v. Government sectors, ministries and parastatals concerned with educational development in the country should employ intellectuals (most preferably, university dons) to create educational contents or academic resource materials and make them available for free for students to consult for their assigned academic tasks or activities.

IJCITR

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VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

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VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

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